

TOBACCO DEPENDENCE PHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECT

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Annotation: Hookah manufacturers, advertising its use, offer a hookah equipped with a mouthpiece with an activated carbon filter or filled with cotton, or offer chemicals added to the water of the hookah and special plastic carbon filters for the formation of smaller bubbles as an additional protective agent. They do not give absolutely no guarantee of safety, and not one type of hookah is not safe for health. There is no clear evidence that a special hookah device reduces the content of dangerous substances in the inhaled smoke. It turned out that connoisseurs of the exotic device are subject to the same diseases as ordinary smokers: cardiovascular, respiratory and cancer diseases. In addition, hookah transmitted in a circle significantly increases the risk of hepatitis, tuberculosis and other infectious diseases.

Keywords: hookah smokers, smoking cigarettes, disinfect the pipe

Everyone knows that when a non-smoker is in a smoky room, his health is in serious danger. The same situation is developing in the society of hookah smokers. In this case, the harm from carbon monoxide, which is released during grange coals, is also added.

Hookah is a special lure for young people who have never smoked before and have not even tried to smoke. This is the real trap — the development of addiction without the person realizing it himself. The trap acts gradually, confidently dragging the person. The initial excitement and excitement is gradually replaced by habit, which opens the way to smoking cigarettes in the future. Unfortunately, youth hookah parties are not uncommon, where alcoholic beverages are used in the hookah instead of water, or smoking tobacco is replaced with a psychoactive substance, which, of course, is unacceptable.

The external forms of the hookah have undergone various changes in different countries. In Egypt, they began to make flasks from pumpkin, from which the pulp was also removed. In Persia, the hookah was especially loved by the residents, who changed it almost beyond recognition. Firstly, they began to make flasks not from nuts or pumpkins, but from porcelain. Secondly, instead of straws, they began to use strong and flexible hoses made from the skin or veins of a snake. These hoses were practical and durable, they got the name "snake tangle". During this period of time, tobacco began to be used, which the Persians tried to use for smoking through a hookah.

People of different classes used different types of tobacco to smoke hookah. For hookah, strong black tobacco from Iran is most suitable, which was soaked several times before use. Sultans, nobles, rich people mixed this tobacco with fruit patocoy, and the people smoked simple black tobacco through a hookah. The sultans also liked to smoke a hookah made from a mixture of hashish, fruit molasses and crushed pearls. Not even all rich people could afford such an expensive pleasure.

What really happens when smoking a hookah and is this fashionable hobby so harmless now?

Firstly, the danger is not only the process of hookah smoking itself, but also the hygiene of this action. The fact is that hookah smoking is a collective event. As a rule, an average of 6-8 people participate in smoking a hookah. At the same time, very often individual mouthpieces, even if cooked, remain untouched or are postponed during the smoking process. Compliance with hygiene rules when hookah smoking in nightclubs is even worse. During the night, the same hookah wanders from one table to another, from one group of visitors to another, sometimes up to 10 times. The waiter, of course, must disinfect the pipe, but the probability that he will do this decreases in proportion to the fullness of the establishment and the demand for hookah. Meanwhile, diseases such as hepatitis, herpes, tuberculosis are easily transmitted through a hookah pipe.

Secondly, hookah can be addictive. But even irregular hookah smoking can make a non-smoker reach for a regular cigarette.

Thirdly, the myth that hookah tobacco mixtures do not contain harmful substances was formed due to the fact that often their packaging does not contain any information about their composition. In fact, hookah tobacco mixtures contain much more harmful substances than the worst of cigarettes. It turns out that one puff of hookah feeds 30 (!) liters of smoke into our lungs, while a whole cigarette of the lowest quality is only 2 liters. And an hour of hookah smoking is comparable to 100 cigarettes smoked in terms of harm to health! What are such excesses fraught with? The most unpleasant consequence is a repeatedly increasing risk of getting cancer. It is because of nicotine that many smokers cannot part with their addiction. Proponents of hookah talk about a "miracle filter" of water, but it would be foolish to believe that all the nicotine remains in the water. Besides, water is not such a good filter, especially for smoke. If the water filtered at least 10% of the smoke passing

through it, then it would be good. As you can see, a person smoking a hookah will receive a significant dose of nicotine, which means that dependence on it will gradually form. So, non-smoking youth periodically indulging in hookah can become a smoker. Suddenly there will be a need to smoke, there will be no hookah nearby and a person will run to buy cigarettes in order to relax, relieve stress, etc.

Proponents of hookah argue that tobacco mixtures for hookah contain much less dangerous substances than regular cigarettes. However, this is not so, tobacco mixtures are ahead of conventional cigarettes in terms of the content of harmful substances. In addition, tobacco packages often lack any markings at all about the content of harmful substances. Proponents of hookah like to talk about wet and sticky tobacco for him, which does not burn, but dries up, thereby allegedly receiving few harmful substances. But this is not so, because the coals in the hookah are heated to 600-650 degrees, and along with the smoke, not only nicotine enters the smoker's lungs, but also other dangerous substances (for example, benzopyrene).

Benzopyrene is a carcinogen (causing cancer) of the first class of danger. Benzopyrene is formed by the combustion of any substance (liquid, solid, gaseous). It is extremely dangerous for humans, even in small concentrations, because it has the property of accumulation, i.e. it is able to accumulate in the body. It is benzopyrene that leads to lung cancer in smokers. In addition, it has a mutagenic effect, i.e. it causes DNA mutations. These mutations can be inherited, and they are extremely resistant. The harm of hookah smoking can affect the health of the smoker's children and grandchildren, which should make him think.

In addition to nicotine and benzopyrene, heavy metal salts and carbon monoxide enter the smoker's lungs, which is released in huge quantities during the burning of

coals and tobacco. Gorenje There is also a danger of carbon monoxide poisoning. Carbon monoxide binds better to hemoglobin than oxygen, so a hookah smoker experiences oxygen starvation (brain, heart, liver, kidneys, muscles and other tissues). The brain is for,

in order to somehow adjust the flow of oxygen to vital organs, it begins to "turn off" the flow of blood to organs of second importance (there is a narrowing of blood vessels, blood enters the organs in smaller quantities). The load on the heart increases significantly, it also experiences oxygen starvation and begins to contract intensively in order to drive blood through the lungs as much as possible and get oxygen. But a hookah smoker inhales carbon dioxide and other filth instead of life-giving oxygen. The heart of a hookah smoker contracts like that of an athlete during training, only an athlete trains his heart and breathes oxygen and his heart does not experience oxygen starvation.

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